

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

MODERN METHODS USED IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF THE HERPESVIRIDAE FAMILY

Mammadova V.,

Institution: V. Akhundov National Scientific Research Medical Prophylactic Institute Azerbaijan

Profession: head of the virology laboratory

Hamzayeva M.,

Institution: V. Akhundov National Scientific Research Medical Prophylactic Institute Azerbaijan

Profession: senior laboratory assistant

Mammadova C.,

Institution: V. Akhundov National Scientific Research Medical Prophylactic Institute Azerbaijan

Profession: senior laboratory assistant

Mikayilova V.,

Institution: V. Akhundov National Scientific Research Medical Prophylactic Institute Azerbaijan

Profession: scientist

Pashayeva X.

Institution: V. Akhundov National Scientific Research Medical Prophylactic Institute Azerbaijan

Profession: scientist

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8198992>

Abstract

The human body is a carrier of many microorganisms like bacteria, protozoa, fungi and viruses. When the immune system works properly, it controls the microorganisms, but when the immune system is weakened due to disease and some drugs, the microorganisms get out of control and lead to serious health problems. Opportunistic infections appear when the immune system is weakened and for this purpose, the diagnosis of HSV virus from opportunistic infections is investigated.

Keywords: herpes virus, Herpesviridae family, diagnosis, herpesvirus diagnosis, HSV-1 and HSV-2

The human body is a carrier of many microorganisms like bacteria, protozoa, fungi and viruses. When the immune system works properly, it controls the microorganisms, but when the immune system is weakened due to disease and some drugs, the microorganisms get out of control and lead to serious health problems. Opportunistic infections appear when the immune system is weakened and for this purpose, the diagnosis of HSV virus from opportunistic infections is investigated. Human herpesviruses HSV-1 and HSV-2 are major human pathogens belonging to the (HSV) simplex virus family. HSV-1 and HSV-2 virus infect people of all age groups but comparatively HSV-1 is more common than HSV-2 (1).

Virulence and invasiveness depend on both viral and immune factors of the host. After initial infection, the virus establishes a lifelong latent infection in the host and remains latent until reactivation. HSV-1 usually presents with mouth sores (febrile ulcers) as the primary infection, and relapses decrease in severity over time. HSV-2 infection usually causes genital lesions that appear about a week or two after the initial infection. The severity of relapses decreases over time as host immunity gradually improves (2).

Infection can be transmitted through blood, airborne droplets, rashes, sexual contact, childbirth, and common objects. In cases where the herpes virus remains in a latent form in the human body, it can recur at different times.

Herpes viruses are large double-stranded DNA viruses. Eight types of Herpes virus have been identified in humans.

Herpes type 1. This type is the most common type. It causes the appearance of fluid-filled itchy vesicles on the lips, tongue, and mucous membranes of the mouth.

Herpes type 2. Genital herpes. It is transmitted during sexual intercourse, but it can also be transmitted through droplets. This virus is very dangerous for pregnant women and can cause fetal pathologies.

Herpes type 3. It is also called varicella-zoster virus. It causes chicken pox, which is common in children, as well as shingles. The lesions appear on the skin, not on the mucous membranes, and last for about a month. It is accompanied by headache, general weakness, fever. After this virus, the human body develops immunity against chicken pox.

Herpes type 4. It is known as Epstein-Barr virus. In this disease, the lesions characteristic of herpes are located in the tonsils, the virus manifests itself with high temperature, weakness, drowsiness and severe sore throat. It can cause oncological diseases.

Herpes type 5 (cytomegalovirus). Many people are infected with this type of herpes, but this virus "sleeps" and does not cause any characteristic symptoms. In the active state, cytomegalovirus is very dangerous, causing serious damage to internal organs. If a pregnant woman is infected with herpes type 5, then the risk of miscarriage, premature birth, and fetal pathologies is high. Cytomegalovirus also causes carcinoma.

Herpes type 6. Causes the development of eczema, lymphosarcoma or lymphoma.

Herpes type 7. Mysterious virus, its only symptom is sleep, and sleepiness continues even after rest.

Over time, memory and concentration problems arise, a person becomes irritable and apathetic.

Herpes type 8. It is an extremely rare and poorly studied disease that affects lymphocytes. It occurs most often in people infected with HIV and manifests itself as small sores on the skin. It is activated with the development of Kaposi's sarcoma.

Some types of herpes infection cause vision impairment, sclerosis, mononucleosis and other complications. At the same time, diseases that damage the immune system can lead to fatal diseases such as AIDS and leukemia (6). The choice of methods for determining HSV depends on the purpose of the study. Testing for HSV 1 and 2 is performed using light microscopy, viral culture, serology, and molecular methods (7). Nucleic acid amplification is most suitable for the diagnosis of acute lesions, as their sensitivity is higher than culture methods. The use of serological tests for the diagnosis of suspected HSV-2 genital lesions is inappropriate because positive results may be associated with chronic infection and a negative result may indicate past infection. (8).

Light Microscope.

HSV infection of the skin or skin mucosa can be diagnosed with a simple light microscope. In the preparation of skin mucosal smears, the smear is taken by gently brushing over the unruptured vesicles. These samples are stained with Giemza, methylene blue, Wright method and the presence or absence of cytopathic effect is determined. The advantage of light microscopy is that it is cheap, fast and simple to perform. (9). This method is used for the determination of HSV from biological material taken from cervical smear to biological material taken during surgical operations. Diagnostics with a light microscope also has its drawbacks. Thus, the sensitivity of light microscopy is highly dependent on proper sampling. For optimal results, the correct sample should be taken from under the lesion and the amount should be sufficient. If the patient is in pain and in a critical condition, this makes it difficult to remove a sufficient lesion. Sensitivity also depends on the stage of the lesion, a positive result is observed in early vesicular lesions. Another drawback of light microscopy is the lack of specificity. HSV-1, HSV-2, and varicella-zoster virus can have the same cytopathic effect, so they need to be determined by a specific test. (10).

Cell culture.

Before the development of molecular methods, cell culture was considered the basis for the diagnosis of acute HSV infection. In this method, a sterile container and an aspiration needle are used to obtain high-quality material. Albumin is added to the media used in the methods to stabilize the viruses. Amphotersin B, vaccomycin, and colistin antibiotics are added to physiological solutions to reduce the effects of bacteria and fungi that may be found in the samples. When samples are used for cell culture, it is important to reduce the growth of other microbes while maintaining virus infectivity. Determination of the cytopathic effect of the virus in culture is possible within 5-14 days (9). The disadvantage of the cell culture method is that it takes a lot of time (11,12).

Currently, the need to protect the cell culture for the emergence of resistance to a number of antiviral drugs is emphasized (13).

Immunofluorescence assays (IFA).

IFA is a method used to obtain same-day results from samples taken from patients. Using this method, it is possible to detect the presence of IgM and IgG antigens (qualitative ELISA) and calculate their concentration (quantitative ELISA). During exacerbation, the IgM form is determined, and in the chronic stage, the IgG form is determined. Thus, this method allows to determine the stage of the disease and the titer of the virus (14-18).

PCR method.

Using the PCR method, it is possible to detect even small amounts of virus particles in biological material. This method makes it possible to identify herpes viruses even before antibodies are formed, regardless of the duration of infection. PCR is based on the method of copying a part of the DNA of the causative agent of the disease and subsequently identifying the virus and its type. A disadvantage of the PCR method is the difficulty and impossibility of detecting viral DNA in patient samples of some viral reactions (19).

Western blot.

Western blot (sometimes called protein immunoblot) is a widely used test method in molecular biology and immunogenetics to detect specific proteins in a sample of tissue homogenate or extract. This method is used not only to detect proteins but also to visualize, distinguish and quantify different proteins in a complex protein assembly. Western blot can also be used as a confirmatory test for Hepatitis B infection and HSV-2 (Herpes Type 2) infection. Western blot is used in scientific research as well as in clinical research areas. Because it can be directly applied to the process of protein identification, western blot is considered a powerful diagnostic tool that is often used in the clinic. (20-21).

The Western blot test looks for antibodies against the infection, not the infection itself. If a viral, fungal, or bacterial infection develops, the body will produce proteins called antigens in response. Antigens stimulate the immune system to push antibodies to fight disease. This test is used to confirm or analyze the diagnosis of a disease after the ELISA antibody test has given a positive or negative result. Western blotting uses a procedure called gel electrophoresis to identify and separate proteins by molecular weight and length. Proteins are placed on blotting paper made of a material such as nitrocellulose. An enzyme is added to the paper. If it causes a color change, antibodies against a certain infection are detected. Since the ELISA test sometimes produces false positives, Western blot is performed as a second test to fully confirm the diagnosis. (22).

References:

1. Roizman, B. K. D. M. (2007). Herpes simplex viruses. *Fields virology*, 2501-2602.
2. Rock, D. L., & Fraser, N. W. (1983). Detection of HSV-1 genome in central nervous system of latently infected mice. *Nature*, 302(5908), 523-525.

3. Gupta, R., Warren, T., & Wald, A. (2007). Genital herpes. *The Lancet*, 370(9605), 2127-2137.
4. Chayavichitsilp, P., Buckwalter, J. V., Krakowski, A. C., & Friedlander, S. F. (2009). Herpes simplex. *Pediatrics in review*, 30(4), 119-130.
5. Kimberlin, D. W., & Rouse, D. J. (2004). Genital herpes. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 350(19), 1970-1977.
6. Rock, D. L., & Fraser, N. W. (1983). Detection of HSV-1 genome in central nervous system of latently infected mice. *Nature*, 302(5908), 523-525.
7. Solomon, A. R., Rasmussen, J. E., Varani, J., & Pierson, C. L. (1984). The Tzanck smear in the diagnosis of cutaneous herpes simplex. *JAMA*, 251(5), 633-635.
8. Roberts, C. M., Pfister, J. R., & Spear, S. J. (2003). Increasing proportion of herpes simplex virus type 1 as a cause of genital herpes infection in college students. *Sexually transmitted diseases*, 30(10), 797-800.
9. Jerome, K. R., & PR, M. R. (2015). Herpes simplex viruses and Herpes B virus *Manual of Clinical Microbiology*. 2007, 1523-36.
10. Durdu, M., Baba, M., & Seçkin, D. (2008). The value of Tzanck smear test in diagnosis of erosive, vesicular, bullous, and pustular skin lesions. *Journal of the American Academy of Dermatology*, 59(6), 958-964.
11. Verano, L., & Michalski, F. J. (1995). Comparison of a direct antigen enzyme immunoassay, Herpcheck, with cell culture for detection of herpes simplex virus from clinical specimens. *Journal of clinical microbiology*, 33(5), 1378-1379.
12. Scoular, A., & Kinghorn, G. (1999). British Co-operative Clinical Group national survey on diagnostic issues surrounding genital herpes. MSSVD Special Interest Group on Genital Herpes and the British Co-operative Clinical Group. *Sexually transmitted infections*, 75(6), 403-405.
13. Scoular, A., & Kinghorn, G. (1999). British Co-operative Clinical Group national survey on diagnostic issues surrounding genital herpes. MSSVD Special Interest Group on Genital Herpes and the British Co-operative Clinical Group. *Sexually transmitted infections*, 75(6), 403-405.
14. Durdu, M., Baba, M., & Seçkin, D. (2008). The value of Tzanck smear test in diagnosis of erosive, vesicular, bullous, and pustular skin lesions. *Journal of the American Academy of Dermatology*, 59(6), 958-964.
15. Langenberg, A. N. D. R. I. A., Zbanyszek, R., Dragavon, J., Ashley, R., & Corey, L. (1988). Comparison of diploid fibroblast and rabbit kidney tissue cultures and a diploid fibroblast microtiter plate system for the isolation of herpes simplex virus. *Journal of clinical microbiology*, 26(9), 1772-1774.
16. Nerurkar, L. S., Jacob, A. J., Madden, D. L., & Sever, J. L. (1983). Detection of genital herpes simplex infections by a tissue culture-fluorescent-antibody technique with biotin-avidin. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology*, 17(1), 149-154.
17. Verano, L., & Michalski, F. J. (1995). Comparison of a direct antigen enzyme immunoassay, Herpcheck, with cell culture for detection of herpes simplex virus from clinical specimens. *Journal of clinical microbiology*, 33(5), 1378-1379.
18. Proffitt, M. R., & Schindler, S. A. (1995). Rapid detection of HSV with an enzyme-linked virus inducible system™(ELVIS™) employing a genetically modified cell line. *Clinical and Diagnostic Virology*, 4(2), 175-182.
19. Tang, Y. W., Rys, P. N., Rutledge, B. J., Mitchell, P. S., Smith, T. F., & Persing, D. H. (1998). Comparative evaluation of colorimetric microtiter plate systems for detection of herpes simplex virus in cerebrospinal fluid. *Journal of clinical microbiology*, 36(9), 2714-2717.
20. Mishra, M., Tiwari, S., & Gomes, A. V. (2017). Protein purification and analysis: next generation Western blotting techniques. *Expert review of proteomics*, 14(11), 1037-1053.
21. Begum, H., Murugesan, P., & Tangutur, A. D. (2022). Western blotting: a powerful staple in scientific and biomedical research. *Biotechniques*, 73(1), 58-69.
22. Mahmood, T., & Yang, P. C. (2012). Western blot: technique, theory, and trouble shooting. *North American journal of medical sciences*, 4(9), 429.